

Inclusive Co-Curricular Activities and Students Social Learning Development in Twelve Years Basic Education Schools in Rwanda: A Case of Nyanza District

¹Sabrine Masengesho, ²Dr. Olivier Mukurira

¹Mount Kenya University, Rwanda

²Mount Kenya University, Rwanda

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8074733>

Published Date: 23-June-2023

Abstract: This study entitled *Inclusive co-curricular activities and students social learning development in Twelve Years Basic Education with reference to Nyanza District*. The results of this research will help school leaders, education policy makers, students, teachers and different persons involved in education activities in Rwanda. Research design was descriptive survey and correlation design. The target population was 492 respondents including 12 head teachers, 120 teaching staff members and 360 learners, 221 persons were sampled and the research instruments were questionnaires and interview guided. Stratified random sampling technique was used for different strata, to determine to whom the questionnaire were given; respondents were selected randomly within each stratum. Quantitative data were performed using descriptive statistics and the SPSS version 22. The findings showed that the majority of the respondents agreed that the co-curricular activities develop students' social learning development. More than 80% respondents were agreed that the co-curricular activities in twelve years basic education schools improved students' social learning development where through interaction and sharing discussions students build their capacity in casualization. Also the researcher has identified the factors of extra activities in twelve years basic education schools for students' social learning development, where the respondents and more that 77.1% agreed that the factors were leadership skills, teamwork, unity and reconciliation and contributed to the social learning development of the learners. As recommendations; the Ministry of Education recommended to encourage the schools to value the co-curricular activities as the catalysts of the other courses and the District of Nyanza was encouraged to motivate all students participation in the co-curricular activities so as to learn effectively while the school leaders and teachers should always encourage learners participation in given activities actively in order to allow them following their lessons and learning in groups.

Keywords: Inclusive Co-curricular activities, social development and twelve year basic education schools.

1. INTRODUCTION

Zhang and Chongying (2013) wrote that co-curricular activities appeared at the first time in College of America 19th century, and were complementary with the curriculum. Many researchers conducted studies related to the effect of these activities in improving learners' welfare.

Children in involvement in co-curricular activities assist in promoting their knowledge and skills with start their life outside of schools. Learner's involvement in co-curricular activities stimulates their interaction with their educators, classmates, parents and guardians. Moreover, via co-curricular activities, workers are developed physically, emotionally,

spiritually and intellectually. The participation in encourage them to interact with the entire community in order to develop themselves. According to Sandra & Anuar (2016), the ministry of education of Malaysia undertook effort to establish a generation that will stimulate honors to the country. The report from cabinet committee report on Muridan policy has put in place educational objectives in Malaysia educate and generate persons with discipline to himself, household, the community learning schools and the country (Sandra & Anuar, 2016).

1.1 Problem Statement

The benefits from social skills are that it may increase both academic and social development of learners and interpersonal relations in schools for all learners (Siperstein & Richards, 2004). Elizabeth, *et al.* (2017), related to contribution of teachers in socio-emotional improvement for students in twelve year basic education schools showed that one of the ways for school to foster students' social development is to promote extracurricular activities, because through them they develop solid relationship between their peers, teachers and other adults. The problem Niyomwungeri remarks is that some school leaders and teachers are more interested in academics than co-curricular activities, and as a result, young graduates are academically fit but without socials, skills and this hinder them to live effectively in society. Moreover, Nzabarirwa (2016) evidenced that educations are asked to adjust their behavior and indicate an adjustment in attitude for supporting their learners to be developed informally but acquiring knowledge via crosscutting issues is not sufficient because they are introduced during others subjects to be taught in the period of 40 minutes, so teachers can take not enough time to interconnect them in her lessons (Nzabarirwa, 2016). And these incite the researcher to work on effect of co-curricular activities on social development of students of twelve year basic education school in Rwanda.

1.2 Specific Objectives

The objectives of this study are mentioned bellow:

- i. To identify co-curricular activities in twelve year basic education schools in Nyanza District-Rwanda,
- ii. To assess social development factors attributed to co-curricular activities in twelve year basic education schools in Nyanza District-Rwanda.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study will be helpful and provide valuable knowledge by improving social development of students through co-curricular activities' participation. It is among few studies that talk about the impact of co-curricular activities participation on students social development in Nyanza District. It is expected to provide unavailable knowledge in this subject. It will form a useful reference for other researchers and readers in this domain. For future researchers in the domain of co-curricular activities and students' social development, findings of research will serve as baseline for future study and will show the area of improvement. Teachers and school leaders will recognize that the regular curriculum is not enough to develop a human capital that is needed in the society. Results would help Ministry of education, policy makers and planners at national level to eliminate the gap between the implementation of regular curriculum and co-curricular activities. Different education stakeholders like NGOs will benefit from the findings, and these will help them to make and revise their strategic and action plans according to the needs and benefits of students.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Co-curricular Activities

Co-curricular refers to education policies or program, which are extra-curricular. According to Bill (2008), co-curricular were designed to supplement traditional curricular activities performed within the community by did not provide the level of learning outcomes. According to Tan & Pope (2007), they were action that assist and fortify the formal curricular. They were known as to extracurricular, school living style extracurricular and outside the class. Stevens when the co-curricular actions, learners assume responsibility in managerial positions, and more they are in favor and leveling their expectations, they are belonging to and the contribution of teaching staff was supervision, mentoring but also guidance without instructor (Chi *et al.*, 2011). Co-curricular activities are more learners based than actual lessons (Tan & Pope, 2007). Via the participation in co-curricular, children obtain knowledge on how to disseminate information, co-operation the other person and ameliorate the living conditions. To give to learners the opportunities to manage co-curricular action will help him to obtain experiences in designing, leadership or help them to discover, develop and use their potentials.

2.2 Types of Co-Curricular Activities in Twelve year basic education Schools

In a study done by Wanjori (2016), they involving speech, and other leisure activities such signing and drawing, football and other related sport activities and discussion among learners acquire knowledge related to the way of living conditions as it is very necessary in twelve year basic education schools. All these activities may stimulate social and economic change within the society. Reconsidering the manual on school administration (1992), describes clubs or groups of students as other kind of co-curricular activities, and put them into five categories which are sport, academic, interest, art, and social services. However, participation in extra-curricular activities for twelve year basic education school relies on how schools are managed and administered such as preparation of chart & models and organization exhibitions (Burnett & Shubha, 2012).

2.3 Concept of Students social development

Social development is improving the individual social well-being so that he can get his full potential. The society is successful when the well-being of its citizens is improved. The social development is investing in people; these require removing all barriers that hinder citizens to reach their dreams with dignity and confidence. The study of Anthony (2016) on influence of co-curricular actions towards the stimulation of socio-economic improvement or change within public schools in Kenya, clarifies the types socio-economic values that students can gain from co-curricular activities, namely, establishing the culture of accountability, discipline, tolerance, cooperation, accepting defeat, spirit of teamwork, establishing a sense of responsiveness, criticism and increasing the culture of positive attitude among learners. Sandra and Anuar (2016), in their study on co-curricular actions and their influence on social knowledge and know-how for the style of living show that the skills to be developed through co-curricular activities are like communication skills, self-confidence, improving relationship, collaborating each other, spirit of teamwork, capable to make a change, communication among students, conflict management and skills in leadership. Lange and Technicon demonstrated social skills from co-curricular activities, namely, communication skills, problem solving, leadership qualities and teamwork (Sandra & Anuar, 2016).

2.4 Empirical Literature

Previous studies done on the role of extra-curricular in twelve year basic education schools have focused on inconclusive results from homework and national examination grades (Carla, 2004). This researcher reiterated that school principals and teachers are more like to stimulate and facilitate parent/guardian to afford enough time to the central place it occupy in improving social and economic living conditions, unfortunately some children did not have a need of co-curricular activities, the important for them is to concentrate in their studies. The researcher demonstrated the complementarity role between co-curricular lessons and social welfare of learners and the entire community (Bill, 2008).

A research carried out in the United States of America by Bill (2008), argued that 46 percent of respondents from parents accepted the pertinence of extra-curricular activities in improving learners social welfare and economic growth of the United States. The first specific objective was to understand the role of sport, music and other extra lesson activities on educational improvement. In this regard, 39% responded in favor of co-curricular action and 41% specified that role of rationality, 80% the contribution of extra-curricular and only 20% did not accept these role. The other question would like to know the American's point of view about the elimination of co-curricular activities in school because they ask additional budget, 62% of respondents opposed to the decisions of eliminating co-curricular activities owing to the devaluation of the role of American Public schools take into consideration co-curricular activities (Bill, 2008). Jacquelyn, (2009) on American study on the role of involvement in co-curricular actions may affect student's success and growth; they researched were learners included and learners not included from three Kansas public college in rural areas. The research has been 20265 joined in academic year 2008-2009. The sample size was 325 in 145 who are included in co-curricular activities are more independent, capable to manage behavior, emotion from families and then those who are included (Jacquelyne, 2009).

2.5 Critical Review and research Gaps

Previous studies were undertaken for examining the role of co-curricular activities on the learner's social development. However, results were inconclusive and were qualitative in nature by showing either statistically significant or insignificant effect. Moreover, diverse types of social improvement may be assessed and give relevant evidences to previous studies. Therefore, no study has been undertaken in Nyanza District. In order to bridge this gap, the present research will be undertaken in this area.

2.6 Maslow Hierarchy of Needs Theory

Abraham Maslow advanced this theory relying on persons the role of development and self-actualization (Maslow, 1943). Indicated harassed encountered by the persons for achieving the predictable results via the forgoing of one another. The primordial stage of needs refers to physiological needs like water, sleeping, air, food. All these are necessary the people's survival, followed by security needs including love, belonging to a group of persons, connection with others, living in a family or household, associations, having friends, team and relational association. The persons expect to bear dealing with others, the next needs are estimation needs was this phase persons for respecting, appreciating, taking into account and value by other owing to the role in community. These expectations are various qualified actions, athletics where persons cooperative. The last one of needs was self-actualization, therefore, persons for achieving or realizing the accomplishment and persons pertinent. They examine the talents and pertinent without taking into account (Maslow, 1943). Maslow categorized social expectations and esteemed expects as psychological or emotional expectations.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The present adopted a descriptive survey owing to its nature in providing responses. Therefore, Marshall and Rossma (2006), descriptive study gives a relevant response and is capable of showing the association between research variables. Furthermore, the most influential design is establishing the relationship between variables.

3.2 Target Population

The target population refers to elements, objective and subjects that respond to the sampled population (Burns & Grove, 1993). The target population is 492 composed by 12 head teachers, 120 teachers and 360 students from day and boarding twelve year basic education schools located in study area.

3.3 Sample Technique

The researcher divided information into three groups like teaching staff, school principals and learners and were selected randomly was employed. The sample simple technique and systematically was used to select the sample to select head teacher, school persons school principals.

3.4 Data Collection Instruments

The researcher of this study collected data using questionnaires and interview as effective tools to get reliable and valid information related to the study.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

In this part the researcher discussed the research findings in line with the objectives. The findings have been analyzed, presented, interpreted and discussions were addressed on the inclusive co-curricular activities and students' social learning development in twelve years basic education schools.

4.2 Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The researcher has characterized the respondents according to their age, gender and the working experience and about the background of respondents. The total number of respondents was 221 including 6 head teachers, 53 teachers and 162 students in twelve years basic education schools Nyanza District Rwanda participated in this study on the inclusive co-curricular activities.

4.3 Presentation of the Findings

During this study the researcher embarked on the field collected data from the respondents. All 100% of them participated in this study and provided their views on inclusive co-curricular activities and students social learning development in twelve years basic education schools of Nyanza District in Rwanda. The data analysis were presented in line with the objectives of the study which were: to identify co-curricular activities in twelve year basic education schools in Nyanza District-Rwanda, to assess social development factors attributed to co-curricular activities in twelve year basic education schools in Nyanza District-Rwanda, to ascertain the relationship between the two variables .

4.4 Identification of co-curricular activities in twelve year basic education schools of Nyanza District

The searcher has been interested in finding out the co-curricular activities found in twelve years basic education and presented them in the tables.

Table 1: Teachers views on identification of the co-curricular activities in 12YBE

Statement	Disagreement		Neutral		Agreement		Mean	StaDv
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
Students participate regularly in ball games	1	1.9	5	10	46	88.4	3.5	2.5
Students participate regularly in athletics	3	5.8	4	7.7	45	86.5	3.9	2.8
Students participate regularly in traditional dance	7	13.4	7	13.4	38	73	2.9	1.2
Students participate regularly in debate and discussion	3	5.8	2	3.8	47	90.3	4	1.5
Students participate regularly in different clubs	5	10	1	1.9	46	88.4	3.2	2.2

Source: Primary Data (2023).

The table 1 describes the identified co-curricular activities in twelve years basic education schools of Nyanza District for students' social learning development. The findings showed that the majority of the respondents agreed that the co-curricular activities develop students' social learning. The respondents were asked if students participate regularly in ball games and 88.4% responded agree, 10% were neutral, while only 1.9% answered disagree. When asked if students participate regularly in athletics 86.5% responded agree, 7.7% were neutral, while only 5.8% answered disagree. When asked if students participate regularly in debate and discussion 90.3% responded agree, 3.8% were neutral, while only 5.8% answered disagree. When asked if students participate regularly in debate and discussion 90.3% responded agree, 3.8% were neutral, while only 5.8% answered disagree. When teacher were asked if students participate regularly in different clubs 88.4% responded agree, 1.9% were neutral, while only 10% answered disagree.

According to Sandra and Anuar (2016), schools that have awareness of the role of the students' development in their social activities development such as self-confidence, honesty, social adaptation, social obligation and responsibility. Once students lose the sense of time management and spend much time in co-curricular activities and even to focus on the importance to their lessons in class, the result for academic achievement increased.

4.5 Social development factors attributed to co-curricular activities twelve years basic education

The researcher has described the factors that attributed to co-curricular activities in twelve years basic education.

Table 2: The students' views on factors attributed to co-curricular activities

Statement	Disagreement		Neut		Agreement		Mean	StaDv
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Fre	%		
Students master language of medium of instruction	12	7.4	31	19.1	119	73.5	7.1	3.9
Students share their experiences	8	5	17	10.5	137	84.6	6.0	4.8
Leadership skills has improved in our school among the students	21	13	16	9.9	125	77.1	7.0	4.1
Students have built teamwork	10	6.1	18	11.1	134	82.7	6.5	4.0
The level of unity and reconciliation has improved	15	9.3	21	13	90	55.6	5.9	4.5

Source: Primary Data (2023).

In the table 2 the researcher described the factors attributed to co-curricular activities in twelve years basic education schools for students' social learning development, where the respondents were asked if students master language of medium of instruction through participating in the co-curricular activities and 73.5% agreed, 19.1% were neutral, while only 7.4% disagreed. When asked if students' participation in co-curricular activities improved leadership skills; 77.1% agreed, 9.9% were neutral, while only 13% disagreed. When asked if students participation has built teamwork 82.7% agreed, 11.1% were neutral, while only 6.1% disagreed. When asked if student's participation in co-curricular activities raised the unity and reconciliation 55.6% responded agree, 13% were neutral, while only 9.3% disagreed.

The researcher concluded the above factors influence the students' interaction and socialization in boosting the learning outcomes in twelve years basic education schools.

According to Tahir, et al (2012), on influence of co-curricular action on social learner's development, found out how co-curricular affect the development of personality in secondary schools' students, they specified those personality traits to be developed which are sociability, honesty, attitude of sympathy, honesty, adaptation, social obligation and responsibility, and co-curricular activities like oratories, debates, sports, girl guiding, athletics and scouting.

Table 3: Teachers' views on factors attributed to co-curricular activities

Statement	Disagreement		Neut		Agreement		Mean	StaDv
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
Co-curricular activities helps mastering language of instruction	7	13.2	4	7.5	42	79	7.1	3.9
Co-curricular activities helps in sharing of experiences	2	3.8	7	13.2	44	83	6.0	4.8
Co-curricular activities helps unity and reconciliation	4	7.5	2	3.8	47	88.7	7.0	4.1
Co-curricular activities helps in teamwork	4	7.5	0	0	49	92.5	6.5	4.0
Co-curricular activities improved our leadership skills	9	17	1	1.9	43	81.1	5.9	4.5

Source: Primary Data (2023).

As it was described in the table 3, the teacher strengthened that there were factors attributed to co-curricular activities in twelve years basic education schools for students' social learning development such developing the language of medium of instruction which is English language in schools of Rwanda, leadership skills, unity and reconciliation, and the respondents have confirmed them at higher level.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

During the study, the researcher has drawn conclusions basing on the researcher questions asked which were; "What are the co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Nyanza District-Rwanda? What is the social development factors attributed to co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Nyanza District, Rwanda? What is the relationship between co-curricular activities' participation and social development in secondary schools in Nyanza District, Rwanda?"

As to whether there was co-curricular activities prapc4irve in twelve year basic education the researcher concluded that there were many but most of them were plays, games, athletics, and other different social activities performed by the students in order to facilitate them learning effectively.

According to the study there were social development factors attributed to co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Nyanza District, such as such as mastering language of medium of instruction through participating in the co-curricular activities, leadership skills development during the play and games; building teamwork the unity and reconciliation.

The researcher concluded that there was a strong relationship between co-curricular activities implementation and student social learning development in twelve years basic education schools of Nyanza.

5.1 Recommendations

After drawing the conclusions and identifying the gap in the implementation of the co-curricular activities during the study, the researcher addressed the following recommendations for the concerned parties:

The Rwandan Ministry of Education should encourage the schools to value the co-curricular activities as the catalysts of the other courses and enhances the implementation of them among all teachers because the findings showed that not all teachers put the co-curricular in action.

The District of Nyanza should encourage all students' participation in the co-curricular activities so that they get to learn effectively by socializing with their colleagues in social different activities depending on the student abilities.

The school leaders and teachers should always encourage learners participation in given activities actively in order to allow them following their lessons and learning in groups.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anderson, J. C., et al (2003). Parental support and pressure and children's extracurricular activities: *Relationship without amount of involvement and effective experienced of participation. Journal of Applied Development Psychology*, 24(2), 241-257
- [2] Astin, A.W (1999). Student involvement: *A developmental theory for higher education. Journal of College Student Development*, 40, 518-529
- [3] Besiwenger, K. L & Grolnick, (2010). Interpersonal and interpersonal factors associated with autonomous motivation in adolescent's after-school activities. *The Journal of*
- [4] Davis, G., (2004). A history of social development network in the World Bank. *Washington DC: The World Bank, Social Development, Paper No.56.*
- [5] Descombe, M (2008). *The good Research Guide: For Small Scale Scoail Research Projects.* 5th edition.
- [6] Dunn, J. S., et al. (2003). Parental ideologies and children's after-school activities. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 46(10) 1359-1386.
- [7] Ewell, P.T. (2007). A policy guide for assessment: *Making good use of tasks of critical thinking. Education testing service. Builder, CO: National center for education management systems.*
- [8] Fawcett, L.M et al (2009). Role of motivation, self-efficacy and parent support in adolescent structured leisure activity participation. *Australian Journal of Psychology* 61(3) 175-182. APS Wiley Online Library, Wiley Press room.
- [9] Fredericks, J.A et al (2004). School engagement: Potential of concept of evidenced. *Review of educational research.* Paper presented at the indicators of positive development conference, child trends. University of Michigan.
- [10] Hamedah, W.A. & Norma, T. (2009). School as the producer of human capital. *Kuala Lumpur: PTS Professional.*
- [11] Hornby, A.S. (1995). Oxford advanced dictionary. *New International student education UK: Oxford University Press.*
- [12] Jacklyn, R.E. (2009). The relationship of involvement in co-curricular programs on community student success and development: A dissertation for the degree of doctor of education. University of Nebraska, Lincoln.
- [13] Janelle, C. (2017). Teaching strategies for teaching in teams. Retrieved from www.teachhub.com/teaching-strategies-teaching-teams. August, 2017.
- [14] Ma honey, R.W. et al. (2005). Organized activities after school and community program. *Mahwal, N.J: Lawrence Erlbraum Associates.*
- [15] Mittal, V. & Kamakura, W.A. (1999), Satisfaction, repurchase intent and repurchase behavior, *Investigating the modeling effect of customer characteristics. Journal of marketing research.*

- [16] Mugenda, O.M (2003). Research Methods: Qualitative and quantitative Approaches. *African Center for Technology Studies*. Nairobi.
- [17] Mukabutera, A & Kabayiza, I. (2013). Abahizi club assessment: *report for the USAID/Higa Ubeho program*. Global Communities Rwanda.
- [18] Normah, Y & Abugohar, M.A (2017), Teachers attitudes towards the use of ECA in enhancing students 'speaking skills. *Faculty of Languages and communication, Sultan Zainal Abidin University, Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu, Malaysia*.
- [19] Parahoo, K. (1997). Nursing research: *Principles, process and issues*, London: Macmillan Press.
- [20] Phi Teta Kappa (2009). International Honor Society. Retrieved from [http://www.ptk.org/hallmarks/09/awards/hallmarks/distinguished chapter](http://www.ptk.org/hallmarks/09/awards/hallmarks/distinguished%20chapter).
- [21] Prime Minister's Department (2007). Datik Seri Abdullah Bin Haji Ahmad Badawi Speech at the mid-term review ninth Malasia Plan 2006-2010, Putrajaya: *Prime Minister's Department*.
- [22] Rashid, A. et al. (2005). Teacher's perception on the effectiveness of co-curricular activities: *A case study of Malaysia schools*. Retrieved from [://www. Scribd .com /4929430 /teachers-perception-on the effectiveness of co-curricular activities](http://www.scribd.com/4929430/teachers-perception-on-the-effectiveness-of-co-curricular-activities)
- [23] Ruhaiza, R. (2007). Co curriculum halted social problems. *Kuala Lumpur. New Strait Time Press (M) Bhd*.
- [24] Salomon, A, (2015). The death of co-curricular activities in schools, *Africa news, pp*
- [25] Sanga, I. (2016). *African research journal of education and social sciences: The Catholic University of East Africa, Nairobi, Kenya. Vol 3. Retrieved from http://www.arjess.orf/education for self-reliance, Nyerere policy recommendations in the context of Tanzania*. University of East Africa, Dalesalaam, Tanzania.
- [26] Santer (2007). Free play in early childhood: *National children's Bureau, London, United Kingdom*
- [27] Stirrup, J. et al (2015). Intensive mothering in the early years: *The cultivation and consolidation of physical capital. Sport, education and society, 20(1), 89-106*
- [28] Tahir, M. et al (2012). Impact of co-curricular activities on personality development of twelve year basic education school students. *International journal of humanities and social sciences. Vol 2*. University of the Punjab, Lahore – Pakistan.
- [29] Tan, D. & Pope, M. (2007). Participation in co-curricular activities: *Non-traditional student perspectives*. College & University .
- [30] University of Rwanda (2017). *Careers and employability service policy*. August, 2017.
- [31] Vogt, W.P et al.(2012). When to use what research design, New York: Guilford.